

IMAGE QUALITY EVALUATION FOR COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY MODALITIES BY MEDICAL PHYSICISTS AND IMAGING TECHNOLOGISTS IN VARIOUS HOSPITALS IN ALBANIA**Disha L.,***University of Tirana, Institute of Applied Nuclear Physics***Spahiu E.,***University of Tirana, Department of Physics***Clarku F.,****Shyti M.***University of Tirana, Institute of Applied Nuclear Physics***ABSTRACT**

Under the Albanian Radiation Protection Regulation, image quality evaluation is a core component of Computed Tomography (CT) quality control (QC) and includes assessment of CT number accuracy, CT number uniformity, and irradiated slice thickness. This study evaluated CT image quality parameters across radiology departments in Albania using an ACR Gammex 464 phantom, with measurements performed by a medical physicist. CT number accuracy was within regulatory tolerance limits for 92.3% of scanners, while CT number uniformity and irradiated slice thickness met prescribed tolerances for all systems. In addition, image quality evaluations performed by imaging technologists were assessed and were found to be absent in some radiology departments, highlighting the need for regular QC testing, improved access to appropriate phantoms, and enhanced technical expertise. Moreover, this study suggests that acceptance criteria for CT scanner image quality in Albania require further development. Regular image quality assessment establishes baseline performance while enabling longitudinal monitoring, patient dose management, and regulatory compliance to ensure patient safety.

Keywords: Image quality, CT scanner, CT Number, CT number uniformity, slice thickness, ACR Phantom.

Introduction

Medical use of X-rays for diagnosis and treatment has proven to be immensely beneficial to society at large. However, unsafe use of X-ray radiation has health risks associated with it and hence it is required that proper care be exercised throughout the life cycle of the equipment (1).

Quantifying diagnostic image quality is not straightforward but is essential for optimizing the balance between image quality and radiation dose

(2). Consequently, the application of a regular QC program is important to detect changes in the performance of the CT system using measurable parameters directly linked to the quality of clinical images and helps to detect problems before they can impact the validity of clinical studies in terms of safety, image quality, quantification accuracy, and radiation dose to patients and staff (3-6). Several international safety standards for protection against ionizing radiation, along with recommendations and guidance, are issued regarding the scope of quality control tests, instrumentation requirements, and testing frequency for X-ray medical equipment, mandating the establishment of quality assurance programs for medical exposure (7-9). In Albania, the technical control of X-ray medical devices has been progressively implemented over the past decade under the regulation of the Ministry of Health, which requires periodic technical inspections at intervals not exceeding three years.

The Institute of Applied Nuclear Physics (IANP) is the first governmental institution authorized to conduct QC testing of radiological equipment, in accordance with Decision No. 404, "On Basic Rules of Radiology Installations in Medicine," issued by the Albanian Ministry of Health (10). These QC parameter tests are performed following the recommendations of the Institute of Physics and Engineering in Medicine

(IPEM), as outlined in IPEM Report 91: Routine Performance Testing of Diagnostic X-ray Imaging Systems in Medicine (11). In our country, the implementation of QC programs by a medical physicist/physicists constitutes a key requirement of the Radiation Protection Office for licensing healthcare institutions to operate radiological equipment. Furthermore, according to the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), QC testing should be conducted by a multidisciplinary team comprising medical physicists, radiologists, and imaging technologists, with clearly defined responsibilities and scheduled testing intervals (12). Incorporating QC activities into the routine workflow of imaging technologists enables earlier detection of potential equipment malfunctions, thereby maintaining optimal operational performance and ensuring consistent image quality over time (13), (14).

To assess the image quality of CT scanners included in this study by a medical physicist, the following parameters were tested: CT number accuracy, CT number uniformity, and slice thickness.

The purpose of this work was to analyze the results of image quality evaluation for different CT modalities operating in various healthcare institutions in Albania and to investigate how these tests are implemented by imaging technologists. Regular technical control and awareness of CT scanner performance conditions help identify opportunities for optimizing CT imaging protocols, reducing patient dose, and enhancing overall patient safety.

Materials and Methods

Evaluation of the image quality on the 13 CT imaging modalities included in this study was carried out by the QC Laboratory for X-ray Medical Devices, part of the Radiometry and Radiochemistry Department at IANP. Image quality assessment of CT scanners was performed using the American College of Radiology (ACR) Gammex 464 phantom, and the measurement

procedures followed the ACR guidelines as approved by the national radiation protection regulatory authority (15). This phantom is made of solid water, making it a physically stable device that provides reproducible results over time. It is composed of four separate modules.

Each module measures 4 cm in depth and 20 cm in diameter and includes external alignment markings to facilitate accurate centering of the phantom during positioning (16), (17). This phantom can be scanned either by a medical physicist or an imaging technologist. In this study, it was scanned by the medical physicist using the respective facility's adult abdomen protocol. In figure 1, is presented the ACR

464 Gammex phantom positioning during performance of QC tests by a medical physicist.

Figure 1. ACR 464 Gammex phantom positioning during performance of QC tests

Module 1 of the ACR 464 phantom, presented in figure 2, consists of five inserts of different tissue materials with known CT numbers: polyethylene, solid water, air, acrylic and bone equivalent to human tissue, and is used to evaluate CT number accuracy. For the CT number accuracy assessment, manual analysis was conducted by placing regions of interest (ROIs) with an area of approximately 200 mm² over the different density materials.

The CT numbers reported by each scanner for all five materials were compared with the acceptable limits established by ACR.

This module is also used for slice-thickness assessment. The slice thickness (in mm) is estimated by counting the number of clearly visualized wires in the center of the module and dividing that number by two.

Figure 2. Module 1 of ACR 464 phantom

Module 3 of the phantom, presented in figure 3, consists of a uniform water-equivalent material and is used to evaluate CT number uniformity. To assess the

consistency of the CT numbers across the image, five regions of interest (ROIs) with an area of approximately 400 mm² are selected: one positioned at the center of the image and four at the periphery.

Figure 3. Module 3 of ACR 464 phantom

After the scanning process, the images were saved to a CD in DICOM format, and image quality analysis was performed using ImageJ software, applying the standard window/level settings specified in the ACR testing guide. The CT uniformity test results obtained from each CT scanner were documented in an Excel spreadsheet and calculated according to the relation below.

$$\text{CT uniformity} = \text{center mean CT} - \text{edge mean CT}$$

According to ACR guidelines, the CT number uniformity should be equal to or within ± 5 HU. The reference CT numbers, along with the lower and upper tolerance limits (LTL, UTL) specified by the ACR Accreditation Program for the five materials in Module 1, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Reference CT number and acceptable limits specified by the ACR

Insert material	Ref CT number (HU)	Lower limit (HU)	Upper limit (HU)
Polyethylene	-95	-107	-84
Water	0	-7	7
Bone	955	850	970
Acrylic	120	110	135
Air	-1000	-1005	-970

Results

For reasons of identity protection, the hospitals included in this study are designated with capital letters from A to M. The CT scanners operating in various radiology departments belong to four manufacturers: GE Healthcare, Philips, Siemens and Canon (formerly Toshiba).

Image quality test results performed by a medical physicist

CT number accuracy was evaluated using a window width (WW) of 400 HU and a window level (WL) of 0 HU. Mean HU values were recorded for each ROI placed at the center of the five tissue-equivalent materials. The measurement results the CT numbers of the polyethylene insert are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. CT numbers measured for polyethylene insert

Figure 4 shows that the CT numbers measured for the polyethylene insert fall within the tolerance limits specified by the ACR guidelines for all CT scanners. The CT numbers obtained from hospitals A, C, D, E, F, H, I, L, and M are very close to the polyethylene reference value of -95 HU. The value measured for Hospital B is near the lower tolerance limit, while the value for hospital G corresponds exactly to the lower limit of -107 HU. The values measured at hospitals J and K are close to the upper limit. The CT number measurement results for the water insert are presented in Figure 5

Figure 5. CT numbers measured for water insert

Figure 5 shows that the CT numbers measured for the water insert in most hospitals are very close to the reference CT number of water (0 HU), except for Hospital E, which recorded a value of -4 HU, near the lower tolerance limit, and hospital G, which recorded -7.4 HU, which exceeds the allowable lower limit. Therefore, it was concluded that all CT numbers measured for the water material are within the ACR tolerance limits, except the one of hospital

G. The CT number measurement results for the bone insert are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. CT numbers measured for bone insert

Figure 6 shows that the CT numbers measured for the bone insert in all hospitals fall between the reference value of 955 HU and the lower tolerance limit. The CT numbers measured for the bone material are within the tolerance limits specified by the ACR for all CT scanners. The CT number measurement results for the acrylic insert are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. CT numbers measured for acrylic insert

Figure 7 shows that the CT numbers measured for the acrylic insert are close to the reference value of 120 HU for all hospitals, except for hospital G, which recorded a CT number at the lower tolerance limit of 110 HU. Overall, the CT numbers measured for the acrylic material are within the ACR specified tolerance limits for all CT scanners. The CT number measurement results for the air insert are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. CT number measured for air insert

Figure 8 shows that the CT numbers measured for the air insert in all hospitals fall between the reference value of -1000 HU and the upper tolerance limit, except for hospitals G and M, which have values near the lower limit. Nevertheless, all measured CT numbers for air remain within the tolerance limits specified by the ACR

CT number uniformity was evaluated using a WW equal to 100 HU and a WL of 0 HU. The CT numbers of the water insert were recorded for five regions of interest (ROIs) in each image. The resulting measurements for CT number uniformity for each hospital are presented in Table 2

Measurement results for CT number uniformity

Hospital	ROI measured CT number (HU)				
	Center	12	3	6	9
A	-1.77	-0.35	-1.14	0.02	-1.32
CT number difference		-1.42	-0.63	-1.79	-0.45
B	-1.93	0.45	-0.89	0.64	0.13
CT number difference		-2.38	-1.04	-2.57	-2.06
C	-3.90	-3.40	-4.20	-3.40	-2.90
CT number difference		-0.50	0.30	-0.50	-1.00
D	-2.70	-3.17	-3.13	-3.06	-3.20
CT number difference		0.47	0.43	0.36	0.50
E	-4.80	-6.20	-5.20	-5.80	-6.30
CT number difference		1.40	0.40	1.00	1.50
F	-1.60	0.20	1.45	2.12	-0.10
CT number difference		-1.80	-3.05	-3.72	-1.50
G	-5.01	-5.72	-5.03	-5.39	-5.71
CT number difference		0.71	0.02	0.38	0.70
H	0.32	-0.13	-0.46	-0.21	-0.53
CT number difference		0.45	0.78	0.53	0.85
I	-0.60	0.11	-0.21	-0.38	0.27
CT number difference		-0.71	-0.39	-0.22	-0.87
J	-1.99	-1.57	-2.26	-0.88	-0.59
CT number difference		-0.42	0.27	-1.11	-1.40
K	0.10	0.59	0.54	0.78	0.84
CT number difference		-0.49	-0.44	-0.68	-0.74
L	1.54	2.72	1.36	1.56	1.46
CT number difference		-1.18	0.18	-0.02	0.08
M	0.89	0.39	1.15	1.47	1.48
CT number difference		0.50	-0.26	-0.58	-0.59

Table 2 shows that the CT number uniformity measurements for all CT scanners investigated are within the ACR tolerance limits. For hospitals E and G, the CT number of water at the central ROI was close to -5 HU, approaching the lower tolerance limit.

Despite this, the overall uniformity of the water-equivalent material indicates that both scanners produce consistent CT numbers across the scanned area.

For scanners with CT numbers near or outside the tolerance limits, it was recommended to contact a qualified service engineer to re-calibrate the devices. Additionally, more frequent QC testing is advised to monitor performance trends over time. In the case of the CT scanner operating at Hospital G, it was recommended to suspend radiology examinations until the device was repaired, and QC measurements were repeated by IANP, ensuring that its performance met optimal standards. CT scanners operating with CT numbers outside acceptable limits could compromise diagnostic accuracy, potentially leading to incorrect clinical decisions for patients.

Figure 9 presents the measured slice thicknesses for all CT scanners included in this study.

Figure 9. slice thickness measurements results

Figure 9 shows that the measured slice thicknesses for all CT scanners included in this study were within the acceptable criteria, showing a deviation of no more than ± 0.5 mm from the selected slice thicknesses.

Comparisons with international studies indicate that image quality assessment in Albania lacks systematic evaluation of noise and spatial resolution parameters for CT scanner modalities (18), (19).

Considering recent developments in computed tomography technology and the critical, interdependent roles that noise and spatial resolution play in overall

image quality, it is strongly recommended that national regulatory authorities in Albania revise the existing quality control framework for CT scanners, incorporating the evaluation of both noise and spatial resolution as mandatory components of routine quality control requirements for clinical CT systems (20), (21).

Image quality tests performed by imaging technologists

During routine technical control tests of CT scanners conducted by the Institute of Applied Nuclear Physics, it was observed that imaging technologists in most facilities also performed image quality tests on their equipment.

However, in some radiology departments, these tests are conducted exclusively by maintenance engineers rather than by imaging technologists. The major challenges identified in implementing image quality testing by imaging technologists in our country include the lack of appropriate phantoms needed, insufficient technical knowledge and limited training opportunities.

These gaps, which hinder effective implementation of image quality testing by imaging technologists, were presented to hospital management authorities. Consequently, it was recommended that structured training programs in QC of diagnostic imaging devices be established for imaging technologists in collaboration with IANP, which offers training in the field of radiation protection field. Hospital management teams were also advised to ensure periodic performance surveillance of scanners within their radiology departments by imaging technologists, emphasizing that regular QC practices should not be viewed solely as a regulatory requirement but as an essential component of clinical service quality. Therefore, if, during routine QC tests performed by the imaging technologist, the measured values of QC parameters fall outside the established tolerances, the technologist should consult with the medical physicist.

Discussion

This study presents the analysis of image quality test results obtained from 13 CT scanners operating in various radiology departments in Albania. Image quality assessment was performed by a medical physicist using the ACR Gammex 464 phantom and ImageJ software. The results showed that CT numbers measured for five materials: polyethylene, solid water, air, acrylic, and bone were within the acceptable tolerance limits for 92.3% of CT scanners investigated. An exception was observed for the CT scanner at hospital G, which recorded a water CT number of -7.4 HU, exceeding the lower tolerance limit. Evaluation of CT number uniformity demonstrated acceptable consistency across the image field of view for all CT scanners.

For CT scanners exhibiting CT numbers close to or outside tolerance limits, re-calibration by a qualified service engineer is recommended, along with more frequent QC testing to monitor performance trends, rather than relying solely on the standard three-year mandatory inspection interval.

Measured slice thickness values for all CT scanners included in this study were within acceptable criteria. During routine technical control tests of CT scanners, it was observed that not all imaging technologists

performed image quality tests on their equipment due to the lack of appropriate phantoms and necessary knowledge.

Prioritizing quality control procedures of these X-ray medical devices by imaging technologists, ensures both optimal image quality and protection of patients from unnecessary radiation exposure.

Meanwhile, compared with international studies, this study indicates that image quality assessment in Albania lacks the evaluation of noise and spatial resolution parameters for CT scanner modalities, recommending an update of current QC requirements for image quality of these radiological modalities. Such an update to the latest regulatory requirements would ensure more consistent image quality, improve diagnostic accuracy, and better align the national QC program with international best practices in CT performance assessment.

Conclusion

This national survey of CT image quality assessment across various radiology departments underscores the critical importance of regular QC implementation by medical physicists and imaging technologists to ensure diagnostic image quality while minimizing unnecessary patient radiation exposure.

Image quality evaluations performed by imaging technologists were found to be absent in some radiology departments, highlighting the need for regular QC testing, improved access to appropriate phantoms, and enhanced technical expertise.

Most evaluated CT scanners were found to operate within acceptable tolerance limits in accordance with national radiation protection regulations.

However, consistent with international practice and recent technological developments, inclusion of noise and spatial resolution evaluation in current QC requirements is recommended, to achieve a more comprehensive image quality assessment.

Compliance with the latest regulatory requirements, periodic QC testing and proper maintenance of radiological equipment remain essential responsibilities for healthcare institutions operating CT systems and national radiation protection authorities.

The findings of this survey provide a useful baseline for future evaluations, enabling monitoring of performance changes in CT equipment over time.

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